

Information sheet 1.01

Growing plants in isolation or under exclusion conditions

This information sheet is a supporting document to Appendix A ('Standardised checklist of risk reduction options') of the Guidance of the EFSA Plant Health Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment

EFSA PLH Panel (EFSA Panel on Plant Health), Jeger M, Bragard C, Caffier D, Candresse T, Chatzivassiliou E, Dehnen-Schmutz K, Grégoire J-C, Jaques Miret JA, MacLeod A, Navajas Navarro M, Niere B, Parnell S, Potting R, Rafoss T, Rossi V, Urek G, Van Bruggen A, Van der Werf W, West J, Winter S, Hart A, Schans J, Schrader G, Suffert M, Kertész V, Kozelska S, Mannino MR, Mosbach-Schulz O, Pautasso M, Stancanelli G, Tramontini S, Vos S and Gilioli G, 2018. Guidance of the EFSA PLH Panel on quantitative pest risk assessment. EFSA Journal 2018;16(7):5350, 94 pp. doi:10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5350. Available online at <https://doi.org/10.2903/j.efsa.2018.5350>

A. Description of the RRO

At origin, plants may be grown in isolation or under exclusion conditions to reduce the likelihood of pest association.

Exclusion conditions are implemented to prevent the entry of a pest (or vector) into a place/site of production (i.e. in a dedicated structure such as glass or plastic greenhouses), and therefore guarantee that they are pest-free. Isolation can be geographical (in an area at a certain distance from the infested area) or physical (e.g. on an island, in an area isolated by physical barriers such as mountains where the pest/vector is known not to occur).

Isolation may also be applied only on specific plant material (e.g. mother plants, higher grade material). Such high grade material may be produced in specific areas of a country isolated from the production of lower grade material or the commercial production for the end-user.

Depending on the type of pest and on the plant material of concern, additional measures may need to be implemented to guarantee and maintain the pest freedom status, and ensure that the RRO will be effective (see paragraph F).

Isolation can be officially managed by NPPOs or managed by plant producers.

Pre- or post-entry quarantine are not covered by this information sheet and are described in specific information sheets.

B. Risk factors

The use of the RRO reduces the likelihood of the association of the pest (at origin) by acting on the:

- prevalence of the pest (or vector) in the source area/place of production,
- pest management, cultural and commercial procedures applied at the place of origin (application of plant protection products, handling, culling, roguing, grading).

It may also reduce spread (e.g. when mother plants are grown in specific areas where host plants or vectors are not present).

The use of the RRO reduces the probability of spread of the pest acting on:

- suitability of the natural and/or managed environment for natural spread of the pest,
- presence of natural or artificial barriers.

The use of the RRO reduces the magnitude of impact by reducing either pest or vector prevalence in plant material or in plant products. In the case of some diseases affecting fruit trees (e.g., plant viruses) this RRO reduces the pest impact extending the productive life of the orchard.

C. Parameters to consider regarding effectiveness of the RRO

The effectiveness of the RRO will depend on the type of organism and its mode of spread. The parameters to consider include:

- Knowledge of pest biology, in particular means of natural spread, spread capacity,
- Host range of the pest and its vectors (polyphagy/generalism versus monophagy/specificity),
- Prevalence of the pest and its vectors in the area considered,
- Detectability of the pest and its vectors.

Isolation in a dedicated structure

The objective of complete physical isolation is to ensure that plants grown within such a structure will not become infested even if the pest(s) and/or vector(s) of concern is (are) present outdoors in the immediate vicinity of the structure. The structure used to grow plants under complete physical isolation may be constructed of different material (plastic, glass, mesh) as long as it prevents the relevant pest or vector(s) from entering the structure. It should also be able to withstand physical damage (wind, hail, storms...).

Use of complete physical isolation applies to pests that can spread by natural means e.g. flying or crawling, by wind or water dispersal, or by transport by vectors such as insects, birds or other animals. The requirements of complete physical isolation should take into account the growth requirements of the plants, the biology of the pests and of any vectors that may potentially be associated with them, particularly their mode of dispersal and spread.

Additional measures, including hygiene measures for staff, may need to be considered for packaging, handling and transport in order to maintain pest freedom of the consignment of plants.

General measures need to be implemented to guarantee and maintain pest freedom status, and ensure that the measure 'complete physical isolation' will be effective (e.g. the place of production should be free from the pest before starting the production, only pest free plant material should be introduced in the physical structure, regular inspections should be carried out). More guidance is given in EPPO Standard (EPPO, 2016) and in Table 1 below.

The main spread mechanism(s) of the pest should be considered when evaluating the physical structures needed. For some spread mechanisms, physical structures are not needed to ensure pest freedom, e.g. viruses that are only graft or seed transmitted, pests transmitted by grafting and vectors only, when the vectors are absent from the area.

Table 1. Recommendations on minimum requirement for a physical structure to be requested for the production of plant material depending on the mode of spread of pests (and their vectors) (from EPPO 2016).

Note that a pest may have more than one mode of spread: in this case the most stringent measures should be selected. +: minimum requirement (more stringent measures can be selected e.g. use of a plastic structure when net of a suitable mesh size is the minimum recommended).

Measures	Mode of spread of pests or vectors				
	Soil	Water	Air (including pathogens spread by rain, aerosols)	Small mobile arthropods (i.e. less than 0.2 mm in size)	Other mobile arthropods
Use of pest free irrigation water		+			
Prevention of contact with drainage water, or lateral and vertical movement of soil water, (e.g. choice of appropriate location for the place/site, creation of ditches, plants raised on benches, impermeable flooring such as plastic cover or concrete)	+(1)	+			
Maintenance of plants in such a way that contact with soil is prevented (e.g. raised on benches, impermeable flooring such as concrete or appropriate plastic cover)	+	+			
Cleaning and disinfecting of footwear before entering the structure or use of dedicated footwear.	+	+	+	+	
Cleaning and disinfecting of machinery before entering the structure or use of dedicated machinery.	+	+	+	+	
Cleaning and disinfecting of working tools before entering the structure or use of dedicated working tools.	+(5)	+(5)	+	+	
Dedicated clothes			+	+	+(4)
Windows locked shut			+		
Windows and doors locked shut when not in use, and when open, windows fitted with appropriate screens				+	+
Protection from rain		+(2)	+		
Double doors			+	+	+
Glass structure (or equivalent solid material)	+(3)		+		
Plastic structure (such as polyethylene)			+	+	

Measures	Mode of spread of pests or vectors				
	Soil	Water	Air (including pathogens spread by rain, aerosols)	Small mobile arthropods (i.e. less than 0.2 mm in size)	Other mobile arthropods
Use of a net of a suitable mesh size to exclude the relevant pest(s)			Not suitable	Not suitable	+
Positive airflow at entry points			+	+	

- (1) when there is a risk of presence of soil in drainage water
- (2) for pest spread by rain
- (3) In areas prone to strong wind which may carry soil
- (4) to be decided on a case by case basis
- (5) if possible contact with soil or water

Geographical isolation

The main spread mechanism(s) of the pest and the characteristics of the location (e.g. isolated by a mountain, altitude, absence of host plants, conditions not suitable for the vectors) should be considered when evaluating the possibility of geographical isolation from an infested area.

General measures on movement of plant material to this zone as well as surveys may be needed to implement this RRO.

The geographical isolation may be a condition allowing the implementation of a Pest Free Area (see the document "Guidance on scenarios for phytosanitary risk reduction").

D. Applicability / feasibility of the RRO

Technical difficulties that may limit the proper implementation of the RRO:

- not all plants may be grown in protected conditions (e.g. trees),
- in tropical countries, the use of a completely closed physical structure may not be possible because the lack of ventilation and the increase of temperature will be detrimental to the crop,
- application of this RRO will increase production costs.

The implementation of this RRO is required in phytosanitary regulation. In EU emergence measures for *Anoplophora chinensis* (Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2012/138)¹ the production under complete physical protection is an option for the import of host plants originating from areas where the pest is present (Annex I, 1. Specific import requirements: A.1.(b) and B.1.(b))

E. Other RROs that may lead to similar effects

All the combinations of RROs ensuring pest free consignment, pest free area, pest free place/site of production and post-entry quarantine measures.

F. Combinations of RROs that include this RRO

Growing plants in isolation can be included in measures implemented for the post-entry quarantine for plants for planting in the country of import (information sheet 1.18 Post-entry quarantine and other

¹ Commission Implementing Decision (EU) 2012/138 of 1 March 2012 as regards emergency measures to prevent the introduction into and the spread within the Union of *Anoplophora chinensis* (Forster). OJ L 64, 3.3.2012, p. 38. Amended by Commission Implementing Decision 2014/356/EU of 12 June 2014. OJ L 175, 14.6.2014, p. 38.

movement restrictions in the importing country) and for the production of pest-free plants for planting (information sheet 1.17).

This RRO is not stand alone. It may be combined where relevant with the following:

- use of pest free plants for planting including seeds, tissue culture etc. as starting material, in particular if the pest is seed borne (information sheet 1.17),
- post-entry quarantine and other restrictions of movement (*from infested areas*) (information sheet 1.18),
- inspections (information sheet 2.01),
- sampling (information sheet 2.03),
- testing (information sheet 2.02),
- surveillance (information sheet 2.08),
- cleaning and disinfecting tools, machinery, facilities and staff (*if the pest is spread by contact or with machinery*) (information sheet 1.05)
- soil (or growing medium) treatment (solarization, vaporisation, fumigation, flooding, removal, etc.) (*if the pest is spread by soil*) (information sheet 1.06),
- use of non-contaminated water (*if the pest is spread by water*) (information sheet 1.07)
- certified and approved production, packing and processing premises, traceability of any material entering the isolation area/structure (information sheet 2.05),
- delimitation of a buffer zone and removal of plants in a specific area (e.g. removal of host plants in a buffer zone) (information sheet 2.07).

Guidance on combination of measures to establish a production under complete physical isolation is provided in EPPO Standard PM5/8 (EPPO, 2016).

G. Conclusion

Synoptic table for the RRO.

Target	Area of application	Expected effect	Main technical limitations of use	Alternative/ combinations
Pest and vector	In the field (open or protected cultivation)	Reduce the probabilities (1) of entry acting on the association of the pest at origin, (2) of spread and (3) impact acting on association of the pest with propagation material or plant products	Not feasible for all types of crops	All the measures implemented for PFA, PFPP/S. Certified and approved premises, Certification of reproductive material, Post-entry quarantine

References

EPPO (European and Mediterranean Plant Protection Organization), 2016. Guidelines on the phytosanitary measure 'plants grown under complete physical isolation'. EPPO/OEPP, PM 5/8 (1).